

THE AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT TO STRENGTHENING THE UNIVERSITY REPUTATION IN ELECTRONIC WORD OF MOUTH AT PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES

MESRA B¹, ARLINA NURBAITY LUBIS², ENDANG SULISTYA RINI³ and AMLYS SYAHPUTRA SILALAH⁴

¹Doctoral Program in Management Science, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia.

^{2,3,4}Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia.

Correspondence Email: ²arlina@usu.ac.id

Abstract

The study aimed to examine the influence of university reputation and students' affective commitment to electronic word of mouth either directly or by using moderation variables. The associative analysis is used to ascertain the influence of two or more variables. This research was conducted in Medan, Indonesia with student research objects. The population in this study is an active student, who had studied for at least three semesters and was at the undergraduate level with a population of 16,039 from five private universities. The sample count of 160 samples came from ten times the questionnaire statement. Accidental sampling was used in this study. Data processing using smart PLS applications. The findings of this study show that the direct influence between the reputation of the university and the affective commitment of students to the electronic word of mouth with positive and significant results. Likewise the results by using variable moderation, namely the affective commitment of students successfully moderating the reputation of the university with the electronic word of mouth.

Keywords: university reputation, student affective commitment, electronic word of mouth

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, there are several levels of education, namely primary education at the first level, secondary education at the second level, and higher education. Higher education has the advantage of academic and professional ability in applying and creating science and technology. All educational procedures are in Law No.12 of 2012 on Higher Education. Higher education is better known as universities in Indonesia in terms of ownership divided into 2 (two), namely government property and private property.

Government-owned colleges are known as public colleges, and private colleges are known as private ones. Private universities are as many as 4,262, while public universities only have 384 pieces. (<https://www.kemdikbud.go.id>). Many private colleges are even more than ten times the number of public universities, giving rise to stiff competition among private universities in the fight for students.

Medan is one of the cities in North Sumatra province, Indonesia, with private universities' growth, which is also very extraordinary. Based on Higher Education Service Institutions Region 1 of North Sumatra, there are 256 private universities in North Sumatra and 144 in Medan. All this indicates that the city of Medan is one of the destinations for students to study.

Private universities are also vigorously promoting their campuses. One of the promotions that can be done is in the form of electronic word-of-mouth promotions (Mesra B, Lubis A.N, Rini E.S, 2021). E-WOM is a form of promotion that is done by word of mouth using electronic equipment. Promotion in the form of electronic word-of-mouth is quite effective because it relies on electronic equipment connected to the internet and today, almost everyone has electronic equipment and this opportunity can be an opportunity for someone to promote.

This opportunity can also be an opportunity for private universities to promote in the form of E-WOM among students. Students will do a positive E-WOM if students also think positively. One that can form a positive E-WOM is the existence of a good reputation in the institution. Reputation is the judgment given by a person to an object because of its achievements in the long run. Likewise, private universities that have a good reputation are known for the reputation of universities which, of course, can be an attraction for prospective students in choosing a place to study.

Several previous studies have differed on reputation in influencing E-WOM, including research (Hidayat & Astuti, 2019; Hong & Yang, 2009; Jiewanto et al., 2012; Lubis, 2016; Supriyatno, 2018; Tong, 2014) Stating that the company's reputation positively and significantly affects the electronic word of mouth (E-WOM), but another with the research that has been done by Arbainah (2016); Rahmadevita et al. (2013); Williams et al. (2012) with a very different result that reputation has a positive but insignificant impact in affecting E-WOM.

The existence of a research gap between the reputations of E-WOM in previous studies caused this study to try to add one variable between the two variables. The added variable is the student's affective commitment which serves as a moderation variable. Student affective commitment is one form of emotional bond between students and the campus where they study so that the student concerned is committed to himself to help in the growth and development of the campus by recommending to outsiders so that it will eventually be used as one of the destinations in studying by students. This student affective commitment is expected to strengthen the university's reputation with E-WOM carried out by students to prospective students. The reputation of a good university will certainly increase the occurrence of positive E-WOM among students and, of course, will be strengthened by the affective commitment of students.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. University Reputation

The company's reputation is complete trust and decision on a company that is given the highest and most honourable award. In a company where the product produced is in the form of a service, then the company's reputation is very decisive. The reputation of a company in the form of brand image, company image, brand reputation, the best name, excellent service, and everything related to the satisfaction of consumers must get priority (Weiss et al., 1999) so that the company's reputation is an assumption from consumers related to the company's ability to provide services and provide the best service to prospective consumers and consumers. The

company's reputation is an intangible asset. A company's reputation will depend on what the company does as an entity.

Furthermore, it will depend on the communication and the signs chosen to be given to the market. The symbol of the reputation and name of the company, if appropriately managed, will present the company to be supported by the community; it will even be precious for consumers. So, it can be concluded that the company's reputation is the public's perception of the company, which depends on what the company did before and what the company will do as an entity (has an existence) in the community so that the company will still be remembered and have a good reputation (Quintana-García et al., 2021).

Adeosun et al. (2013) Reputation is a person's perception of the company both from within and outside the company, with the main key being reputation consisting of perceptions. So, the view of others in looking at the company, because the company cannot be controlled by anyone and reputation is very difficult to manipulate.

Gotsi, M., and Wilson in Hasan and Yun (2017) Define a company's reputation as an overall evaluation conducted by stakeholders of the company from one time to another. The evaluation is based on direct experience conducted by stakeholders who are directly involved with the company, so that a form of communication and symbolism that will provide information about the actions of a company by comparing it with actions that will be taken by other companies, especially companies that are competitors. A company's reputation stems from the ability to manage impressions directly, the ability to build strong relationships with consumer constituents, employees, investors, communities, and indirect issues that come from traders involved through interested observers, such as analysts and reporters.

Urde & Greyser (2016) A good reputation will of course have an impact on increasing profits because with a good reputation will attract consumers' attention to the products that have been produced by the company, investors to securities, and employees to its job openings. A company's reputation influences us in choosing the products we buy, the deposits we will invest in, and the job offers we will receive. The public would instead do business with someone who has a good reputation in their eyes.

In a very competitive situation, if we do not have a good reputation, it is the same as a decrease in sales. Because a company that is already trusted will certainly build a pool of credibility and cleverness. However, the reputation of the company it already has is indestructible. Once we have a bad reputation in the eyes of consumers, it will be very difficult to improve and restore people's trust in us. In essence, reputation is very valuable because a good reputation will be information for consumers in buying a product and a company that is suitable to invest.

Likewise with the reputation of the university at the college level, a good reputation will be a concern for prospective students in choosing the college to enter. Building a university reputation is not an easy thing, it takes a long time so that it ultimately gets recognition for prospective students and for students in a college. In private universities a good reputation is more needed because it concerns with a good name for graduates produced and related also with the ease of entering the world of work. This is certainly very reasonable considering that

students at private universities have paid more when compared to the costs that must be incurred if studying at public universities.

1.2. Electronic Word of Mouth

In its role in the digital era the internet has created a new paradigm in Word of Mouth communication and this is the beginning of the emergence of the term Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM). Hennig-Thurau et al. (2004) Electronic Word of Mouth is a positive or negative statement made by consumers and from former consumers about a product or company that can be seen by many people or institutions through cyberspace called the internet. The dissemination of information through E-WOM is done through online media or the internet such as through email, blogs, chat rooms, face book, twitter and various other types of social media that can cause interaction between consumers with each other consumers, with this online social communication will automatically help consumers share experiences about products or services they obtain in the buying process. Cheung & Lee (2012) E-WOM is a review of an online consumer consisting of analysis and comments generated and posted by end users of products who have already spent their money on the product and are already using the product.

According to H. J. Jeong & Koo (2015) E-WOM communication is a statement both positive and negative written by consumers and former consumers about a product or it can also be about a company addressed to others by using electronic equipment that is of course connected to the internet. Abubakar et al. (2016) E-WOM defined various positive or negative statements made by a person or previous customer about a product, service, or company provided to the wider community over the internet. Gruen (2006) in Arif (2019) E-WOM defines E-WOM as One form of communication media between consumers who do not know each other before in terms of sharing information about a product or service that has been consumed.

In general, E-WOM is that develops from traditional WOM due to the influence of technology and internet developments. E-WOM can be positive and negative experiences made by a person customer based on perceived experience regarding the use of a product or service they have consumed. E-WOM can be concluded a word-of-mouth communication using electronic equipment connected to the internet.

Dimensions in Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM)

Research conducted by Jeong & Koo (2015) Reflect electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) through 8 (eight) dimensions, namely:

- 1) Platform Assistance namely the frequency of consumers in visits and write their opinions.
- 2) Concern for other the desire to help others in purchasing decision making.
- 3) Economic Intensive i.e., the driver of human behavior as a sign of appreciation from the gift giver.
- 4) Helping Company namely the desire to help the company in return for the company because it has been satisfied with its products and services.

- 5) Expressing Positive Emotions that is expressing positive feelings and self-improvement after using products / services.
- 6) Venting Negative Feelings i.e., sharing unpleasant experiences to reduce dissatisfaction.
- 7) Social Benefits i.e., the assumption of receiving social benefits from community members.
- 8) Advice seeking the hope of getting a problem solving after interaction with others.

In this study only used 3 (three) dimensions, namely: concern for other, expressing positive feeling, and helping the company because only these three dimensions are suitable to be applied to universities.

1.3. Student Affective Commitment

The determining factor of success in a relationship is the commitment of each individual involved in living a relationship. Affective commitment is one form of commitment that deals with an individual's emotions. Likewise, the affective commitment of students is student confidence and belief from within students those existing relationships are very valuable and irreplaceable. So that the affective commitment of students will motivate every student involved in a relationship with the college to work together in maintaining the relationship to continue in the long term.

Affective commitment is one form of commitment that relates to an individual's emotions. Likewise, the affective commitment of students is the student's belief and the belief from within the student that the existing relationship is precious and irreplaceable so that the affective commitment of students will motivate every student involved in a relationship with the college to work together in maintaining the relationship to continue for the long term.

Peppers & Rogers in Rehman et al. (2019) affective commitment from a customer is a belief in the importance of a relationship that is very meaningful and a guarantee of hard work to maintain the relationship. According to Bowen & Shoemaker in Erciş, et al. (2012), Customer affective commitment is very important in building relationships by being willing to make losses are expected to be short but to realize long-term gains. Customer affective commitment in a long-term relationship is important because, in a long-term relationship, it is the customer's affective commitment that is the basis of a relationship built by both parties. Customer affective commitment has an important influence that can make customers loyal to a company so that the student's affective commitment can be interpreted as the student's desire to maintain themselves in establishing a long-term, mutually beneficial relationship between the college and himself.

Student Affective Commitment Indicator:

Cownie (2019), there are four indicators of student affective commitment:

- 1) There is a feeling of pride.
- 2) There is a feeling of belonging.
- 3) Attention to the long-term success of the university.

4) Attitude as a loyal supporter.

2. Aims And Hypotheses

In this study, based on the background above and literature review, researchers wanted to try to model what factors influence electronic word of mouth in private universities. Therefore, this study aims to find out two influences, namely the influence of the university's reputation and students' affective commitment to electronic word of mouth in private universities, especially in the city of Medan.

For reasons such as the hypothesis used in this study are:

- 1) The university's reputation it will have a positive and significant effect influence on electronic word of mouth.
- 2) Student affective commitment positively and significantly in terms of electronic word of mouth.
- 3) Student affective commitment moderates' university reputation with electronic word of mouth.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is associative analysis that determines the influence between two or more variables than two variables. The study was conducted in the city of Medan, North Sumatra Province, Indonesia. The analysis unit of this research is a private university-shaped college in Medan City, while the observation unit is a student of semester 4 (four) and above at the level of undergraduate education who is considered as an individual who can already provide assessments about private universities as a place to study. In modeling and solution techniques that will be used as analytical tools is Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM).

As for the population in this study is all students who are active at 5 (five) private universities in Medan City, namely: Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Universitas Medan Area, Universitas Muslim Nusantara Al-Wasliyah, and Universitas Islam Sumatera Utara. The number of samples taken was 160 samples, based on the opinions of Ferdinand (2013) and the sample was taken by multiplying ten times from the existing questionnaire statement. Samples are taken by accidental sampling as long as they meet the requirements that have been set. In measuring the reputation of the university using indicators developed by Urde & Greyser (2016) with six statement items. Likewise, the affective commitment of students by using indicators that have also been developed by Cownie (2019a) with four statement items. As for the electronic word of mouth using six indicators that have been developed by Jeong & Koo (2015).

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Characteristics of Respondents

This questionnaire is filled by respondents with various characteristics, including: at least in the fourth semester with the majority of respondents in the sixth to seventh semester as much as 50%. The minimum age of respondents was eighteen years old with the majority of respondents aged twenty-two years and above as much as 53%. In terms of work with the majority of respondents not working, which is as much as 53%. The source of information obtained by respondents came from friends as much as 38%. The majority of respondents were female as much as 56%. For more details, you can see table 1 below.

Table 1. Summary of Respondent Characteristics

No.	Respondents Based		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Semester	4 to 5	25	16%
		6 to 7	80	50%
		Over 7	55	34%
		Total	160	100%
2.	Age	18 to 20	8	5%
		20 to 22	68	43%
		Over 22	84	53%
		Total	160	100%
3.	Work	Working	75	47%
		Not Working	85	53%
		Total	160	100%
4.	Source of Information	Friend	60	38%
		Family	35	22%
		Internet	37	23%
		Other	28	18%
		Total	160	100%
5.	Sex	Man	70	44%
		Woman	90	56%
		Total	160	100%

Source: Researchers, 2021

4.2. Measurement Evaluation Model (Outer Model)

Validity and Reliability Test

The loading factor value on each indicator shows the validity test value with the Smart PLS 3.0 program. The condition commonly used to assess validity is that the loading factor value must be above 0.70 (Ghozali, Imam & Latan, 2015). All indicators on the three variables used in this study are valid because the outer loading value has qualified, which is above 0.7. For more details, you can see Table 2 of the following Algorithm Smart PLS Output.

Table 2. Instrument Validity and Reliability

Measurement Items	Outer Loading
The reputation of the University (CR = 0,887; AVE = 0,798)	
Good impression	0,708
Good almanater	0,743
Study program according to the world of work	0,751
The university helps its graduates	0,796
Good accreditation	0,735
Good image	0,785
Student affective commitment (CR = 0,856; AVE = 0,757)	
Feeling proud	0,764
Feelings of having	0,721
Attention to the university	0,782
Loyal supporters	0,830
Electronic Word of Mouth (CR = 0,907; AVE = 0,775)	
Helping others with positive experiences.	0,812
Help others to get a good campus	0,791
Express feelings about a good campus	0,715
It's nice to share your experience with others.	0,773
I am satisfied if you help the campus be successful	0,812
Also, support a good campus	0,791

Source: Smart PLS Output, 2021

Reliability tests to prove the accuracy and consistency of instruments in measuring construction. In PLS-SEM, using the Smart PLS 3.0 program, measurement of the reliability of a construct with reflexive indicators can be done by calculating the value of composite reliability. A common requirement used in assessing the reliability of a construct is that the reliability of a composite must be greater than 0.7% (Ghozali, Imam & Latan, 2015).

All indicators on all three variables in Table 3 have been reliable because the composite reliability value is already above 0.7, so all instruments are accurate and consistent in measuring variables. Data processing can enable all valid and reliable variable indicators by looking at the magnitude of the influence of exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables using the determination coefficient test (R-Square). The coefficient of determination (R-Square) looks at the magnitude of the influence of independent variables on dependent variables in the form of percentages. Coefficient of determination (R-Square) with values between 0 and 1. R-Square values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 indicate that the model is strong, medium, and weak (Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, 2015).

An R-Square score of 0.869 means the construction of the university's reputation, the construct of student affective commitment, and its interaction of 86.9% can explain the E-WOM variable. For endogenous latent construction in structural models, identifying a model is very strong because it is close to 100%. Table 3 below shows the magnitude of the R-Square value.

Table 3. R-Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
E-WOM	0,869	0,868

Source: Output Smart PLS, 2021

Influence the Variables

The influence between variables in this study consists of direct influences and influences of variable moderation. The direct influence of free variables on bound variables consists of: the influence of students' affective commitment to E-WOM and the influence of the university's reputation on E-WOM. While the influence with the existence of moderation variables is: the interaction between the reputation of the university and the affective commitment of students to E-WOM.

Inter-variable influence testing showed that the university's reputation variable had a positive and significant effect on the electronic word of mouth at a significance level of 5%, namely (T count 6,513 > 1.96). Variable student affective commitment to E-WOM also had a positive and significant effect (T count 8,971 > 1.96), and for moderation variables (the interaction between university reputation and student affective commitment) could also significantly affect E-WOM at 5% (T count 2,477 > 1.96) with quasi-moderation levels. So, it can be concluded that the affective commitment of students strengthens the influence between the reputation of the university and the electronic word of mouth by taking case studies at private universities in the city of Medan, Indonesia. The more details of the influence between variables can be seen in table 4 below.

Table 4. Path Coefficients

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
Reputation * Commitment → E-WOM	0,038	0,016	2.477	0,014
Student's Affective Commitment → E-WOM	0,543	0,060	8.971	0,000
University Reputation → E-WOM	0,478	0,073	6,513	0,000

Source: Output Smart PLS, 2021

DISCUSSION

Hypothesis 1: University Reputation Positively Affects E-WOM

Analysis conducted with the Smart PLS Program showed that the university's reputation had a positive and significant influence on electronic word of mouth with a T count of 6,513 > T Table 1.96. This is seen from the statistical value of T which is estimated at 6,513, which means that the university's reputation construct has a positive and significant effect on E-WOM. Students at five private colleges in the city of Medan have encouraged positive E-WOM with a good university reputation. The results of the study received the first hypothesis that the reputation of the university had a positive and significant effect on E-WOM.

The reputation of the university is very important by a student at the time the student has graduated and is looking for a job. Because the reputation of the university will create its own image and that will bring its reputation among the industry. Universities will become more competitive in the labor market if they have reliable and job-ready graduates. This will lead universities to create a competitive advantage by attracting the best students and then the best companies.

The university reputation of a university graduate working in a company is found to be related to the performance of such employees. In addition, students feel that studying at a particular university shows their success rate in getting a job and the perception of their wage range after graduation, the company's preference for them in the job market, the student's sense of pride and eligibility for their level in the world of work market.

The reputation of the university also contributes to building E-WOM, because the reputation of the university concerns the good name of an institution. The reputation of the university is something natural and built in a long time. The reputation of the college university is an important factor in the process of creating E-WOM. The reputation of a good university in the eyes of consumers or prospective students is needed by a college. The reputation of this university is so important for the survival of a college, so it is expected to influence prospective students to choose the college.

This research is in line with research conducted by (Dixit et al., 2019; Hidayat & Astuti, 2019; Jiewanto et al., 2012; Lluisa Llamero, 2018; Melastri & Giantari, 2019; Tong, 2014; Zoghلامي, 2018). It states that the company's reputation as a positive and significant influence on E-WOM. This study, by taking the research object at 5 (five) private universities in Medan City, Indonesia also found the same thing that the reputation of the university has a positive and significant influence on E-WOM.

Descriptive analysis of this study related to the reputation of the university was in the good category. Indicators that are above average and need to be maintained are a good impression. Here students already feel a good impression of the campus where they study. A good alma mater also needs to be maintained because with a good Alma mater will help its graduates in obtaining a job. Likewise, good accreditation needs to be maintained, and if it needs to be improved even more because good accreditation will show the quality of its graduates. The image of a good university also needs to be maintained because a good image is one's assessment of the college, if the image of a good college will be able to attract others in dropping the choice against the college.

While the indicator of the reputation of the university that still needs to be improved is a study program that is not in accordance with the world of work so that graduates still find it difficult to get a job that matches their field during college, the university should open a study program that suits the needs of the world of work at this time because however, every graduate wants to work in a place that suits his knowledge during his studies. Likewise, the university has not helped its graduates in obtaining jobs. We recommend that universities cooperate with related institutions that can accommodate many graduates. With the cooperation, graduates no longer

need to worry after graduation later because there are already companies that are willing to accommodate.

Hypothesis 2: Student Affective Commitment Positively Affects E-WOM

Student affective commitment has a positive and significant effect on E-WOM. This is indicated by the t-statistical value of 8.971, which is greater than the t-table value (1.96), and a P-Value value of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. This means that the second hypothesis is proven and accepted. This means that the better the affective commitment of students, the more it will encourage positive E-WOM.

Student affective commitment made by students is one form of emotional bond between students and private universities where they study so that the student is committed to him to help the growth of private universities by recommending private universities to outsiders so that private universities are better known and private universities will be used as one of the places. Purpose in learning. This student affective commitment is expected to strengthen the reputation of the university with E-WOM carried out by students to prospective students. The reputation of a good university will certainly increase the occurrence of E-WOM from among students and of course will be strengthened by the affective commitment of students in the students themselves.

This research is in line with previous research that examined the affective commitment to E-WOM has been conducted by Cownie (2019; Haque et al. (2019); Sumaedi, S., Juniarti, R. I., Mahatma, I. G., & Bakti (2015); Vandenberghe et al. (2017); Yaqub, M. Z., Malik, A., & Shah (2015), All of these studies found that affective commitment had a positive and significant effect on E-WOM. Similarly, in this study conducted at private universities in the form of universities that the affective commitment of students affects positively and significantly to E-WOM conducted by students at 5 (five) private universities in Medan City.

Indicators that are above average and need to be maintained are the feeling of pride to be able to study at this campus and the attitude as a loyal supporter of this campus. At the same time, the indicators that still need to be improved are attention to the long-term success of this campus and the feeling of owning this campus. Both indicators are still considered less owned by students because students are not yet fully the campus where they study is part of him. The campus should be able to provide some kind of stimulus to students that their campus where the lecture is part of him.

Student affective commitment is a feeling that arises from within the student that is influenced by emotional conditions. The greater the affective commitment in students, the greater the Impact on E-WOM among students. What is felt by someone in his heart will usually be told to others; this communication is better known as E-WOM. So, this is clearly the affective commitment that involves more of one's emotional feelings. If the emotional feeling is positive, it will give birth to a positive E-WOM as well and vice versa.

Hypothesis 3: Student Affective Commitment Moderates University Reputation with E-WOM.

Analysis conducted using Smart PLS showed the influence of students' affective commitment in moderating the reputation of universities by word of mouth electronically with a T calculation of $2,477 > T$ Tables 1.96. This I see from the statistical value of T number 2,477, which means the success of the student's affective commitment in moderating the university's reputation construct towards E-WOM. The affective commitment of students successfully strengthened the influence of the university's reputation on E-WOM at five private universities in Medan City so that the results accepted the second hypothesis that the student affective commitment succeeded in moderating the university's reputation with E-WOM.

Descriptively the reputation of the university that needs to be maintained is quality academic services and qualified lecturers. Affective commitment of students who also need to be maintained with the highest value is the feeling of pride in being able to attend college and have an attitude as a loyal supporter of the private college where they study. The combination of the university's reputation with student affective commitment will encourage positive E-WOM among students.

Indicators on the reputation of the university that still need to be improved are still the existence of study programs that have not been accredited or the accreditation period has not been extended so that students feel aggrieved. Likewise, after graduation, alumni sometimes find it difficult to get a job because the private college does not have cooperation in many companies. While the indicator on the affective commitment of students who still need attention is the feeling of having this campus that is still lacking in students and the attention to the long-term campus still needs to be improved among students.

Previous research stating that reputation has no effect on E-WOM is disputed, as the results of the study Castellano & Dutot (2017); Hong & Yang (2009); Jiewanto et al. (2012); Melastri & Giantari (2019); Reyes-Menendez et al. (2019); Tong (2014) It found that reputation had a positive but insignificant effect on E-WOM. In that study, they found that reputation can change in a short time, and consumers can simply move to another place that has a better reputation. Previous research took on objects in service industries such as hospitals, hotels, and restaurants. Differences in research objects cause results that are also different from the results of the research obtained. The difference from the results of this study with previous research is due to the addition of variables, namely student affective commitment as a moderation variable. The success of the student's affective commitment as a moderation variable is the novelty of this study and proves that the addition of variables will produce different results. In previous studies, affective commitment variables were more often used as mediation variables, such as research conducted by (Bahadur et al., 2018; Iglesias et al., 2019; Izogo, 2018; Markovic et al., 2018; Raineri, 2017) which states in their research with the success of affective commitment variables as mediation variables.

CONCLUSION

The reputation of the university has a positive and significant influence on E-WOM because the better the reputation of the university will also encourage the occurrence of E-WOM. Similarly, the affective commitment of students has a positive and significant effect on E-WOM. The affective commitment of students successfully moderates the university's reputation with E-WOM, which is at a quasi-level of moderation. Affective commitment that comes from within a person both emotionally and psychologically will affect a person's acting. Likewise, positive E-WOM communication is obtained from someone who is positive-minded as well. Not to forget that universities also require positive E-WOM communication because one form of promotion is carried out by students who have studied at the institution concerned. In this study, the placement of student affective commitment variables as moderation variables successfully strengthened the influence between the reputation of the university and E-WOM at 5 (five) private universities in the form of universities in Medan City.

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